
Ibn Sina on Peculiarities of Child Care

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Abstract The article reveals the presence of the features of the child's body according to the medical heritage of Ibn Sina. The features of women's milk in the "Canon of medical science" Abu Ali Ibn Sina are analyzed.

Keywords Baby, teeth, breast milk, baby personality

Introduction

The initial fragmentary data on a healthy and sick child emerged in extreme antiquity. Avicenna in his treatises stressed the availability of peculiarities of childlike organism distinguishing from the grown-up and defining the course of diseases, especially in early childhood.

In his book "The Canon of Medicine", Avicenna scribed: "Caring of a child consists in his moistening since his nature is likened to the moisture and in need of it for nourishment, growth and moderate, but the frequent movement" [1].

It is in the nature of him, and nature itself demands it, particularly when he makes a transition from childhood times to the juvenility.

Avicenna till the last details described the periods of formation and peculiarities of each period of a child stating: "when a child begins to get on his feet and move around, it is necessary to guard him against forced movements. It should not be given to him to walk or sit until he wants it himself, by dint of the fact that the legs and spine can be damaged. When a child starts to sit and crawl on the ground, it is needful to put him on a soft and smooth place, so that the roughness of the ground does not scratch him; at the same time, the chips, knives and similar piercing and cutting objects are removed from there. It is needed to protect him from slipping from a high place" [1].

One of the most difficult periods for infants is teething. For most of the children, the present period proceeds very painfully. Avicenna rendered an advisory opinion on how to assist a child in a present period. In particular, he wrote: "when the fangs begin to penetrate, it is needful to counteract the child to eat hard for chewing things, so that as a result of increased chewing does not disappear a substance that forms fangs. In this particular time, it is necessary to lubricate his gums with a brain of a rabbit and internal chicken fat to facilitate teething. If the gums interfere with the teething, it is needed to lubricate the head and neck of a child with olive oil washed by the way of mixing with hot water. In addition, it is important to drip such olive oil in his ears" [2].

When the teeth grow to such a point that will provide the chance to bite, the child puts his fingers to them and occludes them. In such a case, it is necessary to give him a piece of not too dry licorice root, since in this instance it is very fruitful. The licorice root is also fruitful for various ulcers and pains in the gums. It is also required to rub the cavity of his mouth with salt and honey, so as not to appear pains. After that when the growth of teeth intensifies, it is needed to give a child pieces of a lollipop from the juice of licorice or a piece not too dry of its root that he should keep in a mouth" [3].

As it is known that the scientists from ancient times paid great attention to the significance of breastfeeding, physical education and proper care for the harmonious growth and development of a child.

Avicenna in his book “The Canon of Medicine” mentioned about the regime of breastfeeding and ablactating. Concerning the circumstance of breastfeeding, Avicenna stated the following: to the extent possible, should be fed by the mother’s milk, in light of the fact that it as food more similar to the substance of that food which a child received in the form of menstrual blood while still being in the womb of mother. It is this blood that turns into milk and so the child easily perceives it and quickly accustoms to it. Practically it is established that when sucking the pacifier of the mother, the child receives a very great benefit in preventing various sufferings.

Avicenna also drew his attention to this fact that sometimes the mother cannot feed a child with breast milk. He scribed: “if there is any obstacle to feeding the child with the mother’s milk due to the weakness of the mother or spoilage, or thinnish milk, then it is needful to wet nurse who fulfil the requirements according to the age, appearance, nature, the shape of the breast, quality of milk, time, elapsed from the moment of childbirth to the moment of feeding another child, the gender of her child. Regarding the demands presenting to the wet nurse, so we begin with the requirement for her age: we say that the best age is between 25 and 35 years. This is deemed to be a juvenility, and age of health and majority. When such a wet nurse is found, it is required to improve her food, giving her dishes from wheat, spelt that are being decent food. The bad vegetable for a wet nurse is the roquette, mustard and sweet basil, given that they spoil the milk; such effect is also produced by mint ordinary” [2].

In accordance with Avicenna, the milk of wet nurse should possess moderate density and stand out in moderate quantity, its color should be white and not altered, but not be, neither greenish nor yellowish no reddish; it should have pleasant rather than fetor odor; its taste should be sweetish, neither bitter nor salty and nor sour.

If there evidenced diet violation, attenuate appetite, and the child begins to weaken, appears laziness, lethargy, insomnia which may result in emergence of different diseases. Forced feeding begotten by coercion, threats is inadmissible, Ibn Sina prone to thinking that it certainly affect the healthy growth of a child. He considered that “it should be adhered to the customary regimen”. If the regimen is supported then the appetite will be healthy. The speculations of a man of science are that it should be followed, if there is only with appetite, and also not to restrain appetite when it become intense, are valuable they did stay engaged in our days.

After feeding, when a child is asleep in the cradle, he should not be bothered, and the cradle should not be strongly swung. It is hurtful, since the milk in the stomach is shaken, which negatively affects the growth and health of a child. In order to strengthen the organism or for the spiritual development of a child, it is necessary firstly, a slight swinging and secondly, the music or song that sung while cradling.

Offering a number of requirements to the wet nurse Ibn Sina emphasized that the wet nurse should possess good and benign temper. She should not succumb to such bad spiritual reactions as anger, sadness, fear, since it spoils the nature of the wet nurse, which subsequently reflected on a child. The wet nurse should have a well-balanced temper, it is also needful that she was physically and mentally healthy.

Ibn Sina appealed to esteem the identity of a child, to explore his interests, to take into account innate age peculiarities.

The natural period of feeding is two years. If a child has an appetite for something other than milk, it is needed to give it gradually and force him. By topical data, after six months along with breast milk the child should start receiving additional food. To date, this aspect of breastfeeding is relevant as the impact of emotional state of breastfeeding woman on the physical and intellectual development of a child and its disease incidence.

It is well-known that breastfeeding provides the baby with necessary food and simultaneously is a protection against microbes. However, the beneficial effect of breastfeeding bears a much broader sense.

It is proven that the peculiarities of mother’s milk are outlined as follows:

1. Unique chemical composition providing a baby in optimal ratios will all needed for the growth with food substances with the least spending of energy for assimilation.
2. Bactericidal ability at the expense of the content of immunoglobulins, lysozyme, lactoferrin, leucocytes ensuring a child a guard against the infections.

3. Prophylactic properties in regard to allergic disorders. Mother's milk is a materialized tenderness of the mother. Breastfeeding begets positive emotive effect in a child. Positive emotive effects not only advance the intellectual capability of a child but also teach him the warmest human emotions and actions, that is, tenderness, attention to the state of mind of the other person, affection.

In one and in itself, the emotion can be caused also by other means on action of mother's milk diametrically opposite to the effect of artificial causative agent positive of emotive effect: mother's milk linked with the world, makes it more joyful and closer. Mother makes the world for a child joyful and happy. Educational background of the woman, that is, mother should be very broad, since it gives groundings of world outlook, world perception and worldview. The cruciality of this in human life is hard to dramatize.

The physical impact of the mother in the course of breastfeeding leads to the mental synchronization of a child with her. It allows the most effective teach a child, in this the mother cannot be substituted by anyone else. On the ground of synchronization develops in a child such beautiful human qualities as sensitivity, attention, care, mercy and kindness. Most importantly, in this particular it is possible to observe grounds of human socialization. Particularly emotional wealth of the relationship between mother and child is thrown in breastfeeding, that is, the capital of education.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina scribed: "As a sunbeam is of necessity for all living on earth, so the mother's milk is of necessity for a growing child" [1].

These guidelines are deemed to be relevant at all times.

References

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